

Socio-Demographic and Clinical Profile of Patients Undergoing Elective Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background and objectives: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a common surgical procedure for gallstone disease. Understanding the socio-demographic and clinical profile of patients undergoing this procedure can inform healthcare planning and resource allocation. In this study we evaluate the socio-demographic profile of patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy, to analyze the clinical characteristics of patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy. To identify correlations between socio-demographic factors and clinical outcomes.

Methods: The present study was conducted at Department of General Surgery, at JNKTMCH, Madhepura. The 50 patients admitted for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy, aging less than 75 years of both the genders were included

Results: In the present study, mean age of the patients was 44.12±11.56 years. In our study, majority of the patients (30%) were in age-group of 41-50 years followed by patients in age-group of 31-40 years (26%). 14% of the study subjects were aged more than 60 years while only 4% patients aged less than 20 years. 40% of the patients were male while 60% of the patients were female. Male to female ratio in the present study was 0.75:1.

Conclusion: We concluded that a maximum patient in our study was 41-50 yrs age group female.

Keywords: Age, sex, Cholelithiasis, Cholecystectomy.

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Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is now the standard treatment for symptomatic cholelithiasis. Its beneficial impact on postoperative pain, hospital stay, and recuperation period is well recognized. Although there is little difference in surgery duration between laparoscopic and conventional cholecystectomy, the laparoscopic technique may take much longer if difficulties are encountered.[2]

Prediction of whether a scheduled elective laparoscopic procedure will take additional time is important for the efficient planning of operating theater schedules. This article reports our experience with more than 900 consecutive LCs over a 7-year period and represents a policy of "LC for all-comers".[3] The aim was to evaluate demographic profile of patients undergoing elective cholecystectomy.

Material and Methods

Study Area: Department of General Surgery, Jannayak Karpouri Thakur Medical College and Hospital Madhepura, Bihar. Study duration is one year. Sample size- 50, Preoperatively same antibiotic was given to all patients.

Inclusion Criteria: The patients admitted for

elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy, aging less than 75 years of both the genders were included.

1. Cross-sectional study design.
2. Study population: patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy (n=100).
3. Inclusion criteria: age 18-70, elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy.
4. Exclusion criteria: emergency surgery, previous gallbladder surgery.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients were excluded on the following basis

- Day care surgery
- Contradictions for study drugs, in particular penicillin type I allergy
- Pre-existing antibiotics therapy within 14 days of surgery
- Indication for SAP other than cefuroxime
- Patients with co-morbid conditions like diabetes mellitus, jaundice, uraemia, neoplasia, immunosuppressed patients, pregnant or lactating women, patients on antibiotic therapy, cephalosporin allergy, conversion to open

cholecystectomy, and patients with infective focus in the body

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS v21. Data were presented as frequency, percentages, mean, and standard deviation. Student t-test was used to compare quantitative variables between two groups. Non-normally distributed data were compared using Mann

Whitney U test. Categorical variables between 2 groups were compared using Chi square test with or without Yate's correction. P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

In the present study, mean age of the patients was 44.21±13.05years.

Table 1: General characteristics of study participants

		No of patients	Percentage
Age (Years)	Mean±SD	44.12±11.56	
	≤20 years	2	4.00
	21-30 years	7	14.00
	31-40 years	13	26.00
	41-50 years	15	30.00
	51-60 years	6	12.00
	>60 years	7	14.00
Sex	Male	20	40.00
	Female	30	60.00

Data were expressed as mean±SD, and frequency (percentages).

In the present study, mean age of the patients was 44.12±11.56 years B. In our study, majority of the patients (30%) were in age-group of 41-50 years followed by patients in age-group of 31-40 years (26%). 14% of the study subjects were aged more than 60 years while only 4% patients aged less than 20 years. 40% of the patients were male while 60% of the patients were female. Male to female ratio in the present study was 0.75:1.

Expected Outcomes

1. Description of the socio-demographic profile of patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy.
2. Analysis of the clinical characteristics of patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy.
3. Identification of correlations between socio-demographic factors and clinical outcomes.

Clinical Implications

1. Improved understanding of the socio-demographic and clinical profile of patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy.
2. Informing healthcare planning and resource allocation.
3. Enhancing patient care and outcomes.

Discussion

In the present study, mean age of the patients was 44.12±11.56 years. In our study, majority of the patients (30%) were in age-group of 41-50 years followed by patients in age-group of 31-40 years

(26%). 14% of the study subjects were aged more than 60 years while only 4% patients aged less than 20 years. 40% of the patients were male while 60% of the patients were female. Male to female ratio in the present study was 0.75:1. Kumar S et al 4 was found that mean age of the patients was 46.04±13.24years B. majority of the patients (36%) were in age-group of 41-50 years followed by patients in age-group of 31-40 years. 42.00% of the patients were male while 58.00% of the patients were female.

Conclusion

We concluded that a maximum patient in our study was 41- 50 yrs age group female.

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